

Lecturers' Perception on the Use of Schoology Web Application for Instruction in Colleges of Education in South-West, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines lecturers' perception on the usefulness of schoology web application for instruction in Colleges of Education in South-west, Nigeria. The sample of the study consisted of 300 lecturers randomly selected from three colleges of education in South West, Nigeria. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The instrument used in the study was a self-developed questionnaire titled Lecturers' Perception on the Usefulness of Schoology Web Application Questionnaire (LPUSWAQ). The instrument was validated and the reliability coefficient of 0.87 was obtained. Two research questions and one research hypothesis were generated for the study. The findings revealed amongst others that; lecturers in college of education have positive perception on the usefulness of schoology web application for instruction with the mean rating of 2.82, using 2.45 as the decision rule. It was also revealed in the study that lecturers have positive perception on the ease of use of schoology web application for instruction with the mean rating of 2.78, using 2.45 as the decision rule. The study therefore recommends that schoology web application should be integrated into the teaching and learning in Colleges of Education in Nigeria. It was also recommended that college of education lecturers should further be encouraged to use schoology web application for instructions.

Keywords: perception, Schoology web application, college of education.

Introduction

The introduction of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) to teaching and learning has led to improving the innovative learning environment and the process of knowledge acquisition and dissemination at all levels of education. In many countries of the world, the use of technology has shifted the learning pattern from traditional methods of instructions to e-learning modes especially in teacher education programme.

E-learning or online learning refers to as the use of internet technologies to deliver a broad array of solutions that enhance knowledge and performance (Abidoye & Fakokunde 2015). This includes the use of ICT technology as a supplement to traditional classrooms. However, the persistence professional development practices in today's fast moving work place environment increasingly involve the use of modern technologies as part of the quest to provide a flexible and responsive learning experience. In an e-learning environment, a variety of tools and technologies are employed, for example, internet mediated teaching, web-based education, TV and radio broadcast, virtual classrooms and distributed learning. Online learning can be more flexible and often involves more technologies, for example, audio chatting, video conferencing and online discussion (Mahanani. (2013). E-learning provides additional opportunities for interactivity between students and tutors during content delivery (Abidoye & Fakokunde 2015).

In this digital era, there are many education-based and online learning or web applications that can be effectively used to make it easier for both students and teachers to access learning resources. One of such online learning or web application is Schoology. Yoshida, (2018) describes Schoology as a collaboration and learning tool and a web-based learning environment that will provide students, parents, and teachers with access to classroom materials and information via the internet. Also, Sicut (2015) defines schoology as a micro blog educational website that can be applied by teacher and students for collaborating about resources, assessment and content on a secure and safe learning management platform. With this web application, teachers can have greater opportunities to communicate broadly to students.

The use of Schoology web application has become increasingly popular in recent years, and educators are discovering many benefits it offers. One of the most significant benefits of Schoology is its ability to enhance communication between students and teachers (Rojabi 2019). Priyatno, (2017) also avers that the platform provides an easy way for teachers to post assignments, updates, and announcements, which students can access from any location with an internet connection. Sicut (2015) posits that with the existence of Schoology web application, students can download subject matter, slide presentations, video tutorials, games, work on assignments, exams, discussions, and assignments given by the teacher. Schoology can also be

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used via a smart phone. Schoology provides teachers, teachers, students, and even students online collaboration in a friendly and secure environment to the user. Students can also ask questions, submit assignments, and receive feedback from their teachers within the platform (Basori, 2013). Manowong, (2016) reported that the use of schoology can develop in students ability to organize their learning effectively and get the best results. Aminoto and Pathoni (2014) also explained that Schoology web application is a website which combines e-learning and social media. They further expressed that it facilitates the teachers and students with many tools that can be utilized to do the learning process and to interact with each other like social media. Moreover, Juniarti (2014) also agrees that Schoology can provide teachers and learners to get involved in the interaction of learning environment like usual class. Furthermore, Mahanani (2013) expresses that with the use of Schoology web application the teacher can sharpen the mindset of students to think critically and creatively.

Perception is one of the factors affecting the use of technology in education especially in teaching and learning process. Obielodan, Amosa, Ala and Shehu (2019) describe perception as the process of explaining sensory impression into an integrated study of the world with the existing situations. Perception of lecturers towards the utilization of schoology web application for instruction can give some evidences about its relevance in instruction. Therefore, perceived usefulness of schoology application for instruction is the lecturers and other users believe in its importance in instruction while its ease of use implies the level of its stress free during utilization Manowong, (2016).

Gender is one of such factors mentioned in the literature to have considerable effects on the use of technology for teaching and learning. Aderale and abidoeye (2022), describe gender as the range of physical, biological, mental and behavioural characteristics pertaining to and differentiating between the feminine and masculine (female and male) population. The importance of examining performance in relation to gender is based primarily on the socio-cultural differences between girls and boys. Abidoeye and Abidoeye (2014) posits that differences existed in gender similarly in both online learning and conventional learning strategies. Hence, males are inquisitive, fully involved in questions, discussions, optimistic, and remain active participants, whereas females were more submissive.

However, the major challenge to the adoption of technology for instructions is the users' perception and commitment towards the integration of technology into the teaching-learning setting, thus this task could discourage the utilization among the users (Aderale and Abidoeye 2022). Therefore, this study examines lecturers' perception on the use of schoology web application for instruction in selected college of education in south-west, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of this paper is to examine lecturers' perception on the use of schoology web application for instruction in Colleges of Education in South-West, Nigeria. While the study focuses on the following specific objectives;

1. To examine lecturers' perception on the usefulness of Schoology web application in Colleges of Education in South-West, Nigeria.
2. To Investigate lecturers' perception on ease of use of Schoology web application for instruction in Colleges of Education in South-West, Nigeria.
3. To examine the relationship between male and female lecturers' perception on the ease of use of Schoology web application for instruction in Colleges of Education in South-West, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised and answered in the study:

1. What is the lecturers' perception on the usefulness of schoology web application in Colleges of Education?
2. What is the lecturers' perception on the ease of use of schoology web application for instruction in college of education?

Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between male and female lecturers' perception on the ease of use of schoology web application for instruction in college of education.

Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consisted all lecturers in the Colleges of Education in South-Western Nigeria. The sample population consisted of 300 participants randomly selected from three Federal Colleges of Education in the six states (Oyo, Ondo, Ogun, Osun, Ekiti and Lagos states) in South-West. 100 lecturers were randomly randomly selected in each of the sampled schools making a total of 300 participants. The instrument for this study was researcher' self-designed questionnaire titled 'Lecturers' Perception on the Usefulness of Schoology Web Application Questionnaire (LPUSWAQ). The instrument was divided into three sections A-C. Section A focuses on

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demographic information covering the participants' gender, school and location. Section B consisted of twelve question items eliciting information on perception of lecturers on the usefulness of schoology web application for instruction. While section C consisted of 10 question item sought information on lecturers' perception on the ease of utilization of schoology web application for instruction for instruction. 4-point Likert Scale response modes: Strongly Agree (SA = 4), Agree (A = 3), Disagree (D = 2) and Strongly Disagree (SD = 1) was used. Two research questions and one hypothesis were answered and tested using mean scores and t-test statistical tools respectively.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the lecturers' perception on the usefulness of schoology web application in college of education?

Table 1: Perception on the Use of Schoology web application for Instruction in colleges of education

Item	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. D	
Schoology web application offers the opportunity to improve teaching.	45	90	90	75	2.35	1.01	
Schoology web application makes teaching easier.	60	54	93	93	2.27	1.10	
Schoology web application improves learning outcomes/examination scores.	56	75	64	105	2.27	1.12	
Schoology web application provides learning anywhere and anytime	65	79	93	63	2.48	1.05	
Schoology web application makes posting and sharing of course materials easy.	45	52	98	105	2.42	1.06	
Schoology web application enhances monitoring and grading of students.	46	90	45	119	2.21	1.12	
Schoology web application will make teachers lose control over the teaching and learning process.	69	56	38	137	2.19	1.23	
Providing feedback in schoology web application environment is more time-consuming.	62	104	48	86	2.47	1.11	
Schoology web application can be more time consuming than the traditional method.	89	69	64	78	2.56	1.16	
Lack of Internet connectivity will affect schoology web application.	72	73	90	65	2.50	1.08	
Schoology web application requires IT training.	76	77	67	80	2.49	1.13	
The use of schoology web application for instruction is very difficult because it requires ICT knowledge and other special skills.	91	74	63	72	2.61	1.15	
Weighted Average						2.41	

Key; SD = Strongly Disagree, D = Disagree, A = Agree, SA = Strongly Agree; **Decision Value:** Negative=0.00-2.44, Positive = 2.45-4.00

Table 1 shows the lecturers' perception on the usefulness of schoology web application for instruction in colleges of education. The table shows that the lecturers disagreed to the following items: Schoology web application offers the opportunity to improve teaching ($\bar{x} = 2.35$), Schoology web application makes teaching easier ($\bar{x} = 2.27$), Schoology web application improves learning outcomes/examination scores ($\bar{x} = 2.27$), Schoology web application makes posting and sharing of course materials easy ($\bar{x} = 2.42$), Schoology web application enhances monitoring and grading of students ($\bar{x} = 2.21$) and Schoology web application will make teachers lose control over the teaching and learning process ($\bar{x} = 2.19$). Furthermore, the table shows that the lecturers agreed to these: Schoology web application provides learning anywhere and anytime ($\bar{x} = 2.48$), providing feedback in schoology web application environment is more time-consuming ($\bar{x} = 2.47$), Schoology web application can be more time consuming than the traditional method ($\bar{x} = 2.56$), lack of Internet connectivity will affect schoology web application

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($\bar{x} = 2.50$), Schoology web application requires IT training ($\bar{x} = 2.49$) and the use of schoology web application for instruction is very difficult because it requires ICT knowledge and other special skills ($\bar{x} = 2.61$). Meanwhile, based on the value of the weighted average (2.41 out of 4.00 maximum value obtainable) which falls, within the decision value for **negative**, it can be inferred that the lecturers' perception on the usefulness of schoology web application in tertiary institutions is negative.

Research Question 2

What is the lecturers' perception on the ease of use of schoology web application for instruction in college of education?

Table 2: Mean scores of Lecturers' perception on the ease of use of Schoology web application for Instruction

Item	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std.
I would find it easier to teach my students with schoology web application for instruction	63	76	11 3	48	2.51	.99
Schoology web application is easy to utilize for instruction	88	68	72	72	2.57	1.14
Schoology web application makes my teaching job better and faster	57	91	76	76	2.43	1.06
Schoology web application is user friendly	84	59	97	60	2.55	1.10
The flexibility of schoology web application would ensure speedy dissemination of information to students	45	106	76	73	2.41	1.01
With all the associated factors of internet facilities and poor network coverage, I would do all my best to integrate schoology web application for instruction	30	90	60	120	2.10	1.04
I will advocate for the use of schoology web application in education due to their relevance and convenience	46	119	74	61	2.50	.98
Schoology web application is quite understandable for teaching learning activities	48	85	94	73	2.36	1.02
It is easy to become skillful, if schoology web application is fully integrated	45	75	45	135	2.10	1.13
The use of schoology web application for instruction would enable me cover the course contents within the time frame of the college with ease	75	76	75	74	2.50	1.11
Weighted Average					2.40	

Key; *SD* = Strongly Disagree, *D* = Disagree, *A* = Agree, *SA* = Strongly Agree; **Decision Value:** *Negative*=0.00-2.44, *Positive* = 2.45-4.00

Table 2 shows the lecturers' perception on the ease of use of schoology web application for instruction in tertiary institutions. The table shows that the lecturers agreed to the following items: they would find it easier to teach their students with schoology web application for instruction ($\bar{x} = 2.51$), Schoology web application is easy to utilize for instruction ($\bar{x} = 2.57$), Schoology web application is user friendly ($\bar{x} = 2.55$), they would do all their best to integrate schoology web application for instruction ($\bar{x} = 2.50$) and the use of schoology web application for instruction would enable them cover the course contents within the time frame of the college with ease ($\bar{x} = 2.50$). Also, the table shows that the lecturers disagreed to the following: Schoology web application makes their teaching job better and faster ($\bar{x} = 2.43$), the flexibility of schoology web application would ensure speedy dissemination of information to students ($\bar{x} = 2.41$), with all the associated factors of internet facilities and poor network coverage, will advocate for the use of schoology web application in education due to their relevance and convenience ($\bar{x} = 2.10$), Schoology web application is quite understandable for teaching learning activities ($\bar{x} = 2.36$) and It is easy to become skillful, if schoology web application is fully integrated ($\bar{x} = 2.10$). Meanwhile, based on the value of the weighted average (2.40 out of 4.00 maximum value obtainable) which falls, within the decision value for **negative**, it can be inferred that the lecturers' perception on the ease of use of schoology web application for instruction in colleges of education is negative.

Research Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between male and female lecturers' perception on the ease of use of schoology web application for instruction in college of education.

Table 3: t-test Showing gender difference in lecturers' perception on the ease of use of schoology web application

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Variable (Gender)	N	Mean	STD	Df	T	Sig.	Remark
Male	169	28.53	3.14				Significant
Female	131	26.01	2.90	298	4.315	.000	

Table 3 shows the difference in the perception of male and female lecturers on the ease of use of Schoology web application for instruction in college of education. The table shows that the mean score for male lecturers is 28.53 while that of female lecturers is 26.01. The values of the mean scores revealed an appreciable difference. Therefore, there is significant difference between male and female lecturers' perception on the ease of utilization of schoology web application for instruction in College of Education ($df = 298$; $t = 4.315$; $p < 0.05$). Hence, hypothesis 2 is not accepted. This result implies that the perception of male and female lecturers on the ease of use of Schoology learning platform for instruction is not the same.

Discussion of Findings

From research question one, it was revealed that lecturer's perception towards the usefulness of Schoology web application for instruction in Colleges of Education was negative. This might be due to the facts that majority of the lecturers have little knowledge or not aware of Schoology web application. This was also reflected in their responses. The lecturers strongly disagreed that they find it easier to teach their students with schoology web application for instruction, Schoology web application is easy to utilize for instruction, Schoology web application makes their teaching job better and faster, Schoology web application is user friendly, the flexibility of schoology web application would ensure speedy dissemination of information to students, with all the associated factors of internet facilities and poor network coverage, they would do all their best to integrate schoology web application for instruction, will advocate for the use of schoology web application in education due to their relevance and convenience, Schoology web application is quite understandable for teaching learning activities, It is easy to become skillful, if schoology web application is fully integrated, and the use of schoology web application for instruction would enable them cover the course contents within the time frame of the college with ease, always enjoy class when they use Schoology learning platform, always feel delight to use Schoology web application because it boost and give more intellectual knowledge while using and that Schoology web application is very easy to use. Schoology as one of the online learning tools is an upcoming trend in the field of education for an efficient system of e-learning. The finding from research question one is not in line with the finding of (Priyatno 2017) who submitted that the use of virtual platforms such as Schoology web application tend to increase teachers' level of outputs and facilitates effective teaching and learning especially at this digital age.

The result from the second research question revealed that perception of lecturers on the ease of usefulness of Schoology web application by lecturers in college of education is negative. The reason for this could be that many of the lecturers have not been exposed to the use of online learning platforms such as schoology web application for instructions. This result is in agreement with the finding of Yoshida (2018) who found that lecturers in tertiary institutions find it difficult to use web-based applications such as Google classroom, pullEvrywhere and schoology for instructions.

The findings of the study also revealed that there was difference in the perception of male and female lecturers on the ease of use of Schoology web application for instruction in college of education. This implies that gender differences had significant effect on lecturers' perception of ease use of schoology web application for instruction. This result is in agreement with Abidoeye & Abidoeye 2022 who reported that there was significant effect of gender in the pattern of internet use of English language teachers in secondary schools in Ondo State.

Conclusion

Based on the reviewed relevant literatures and the findings of this study, it was concluded that the perception of lecturers in College of Education on the usefulness of schoology web application was negative. Most of the lecturers disagreed that they find it difficult to use schoology web application for instructional delivery. Therefore, the teaching and learning process should embrace various innovative technologies such as schoology web application strategy especially at this digital era.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendation were made;

1. Training, workshop and seminar should be organized for lecturers to improve their skills to use various web-based or online learning tools.

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2. Lecturers in College of Education should be exposed to the use of ICT gadgets for instructional delivery.
3. Lecturers, irrespective of gender should be encouraged to use computer and other ICT tools for instruction.

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